

INFLUENCE OF FAMILY ON SUBSTANCE USE DISORDER

Dr. Khalida Rauf^{*1}, Dr. Summaiya Rehman²^{*1}Professor SZABIST University²Assistant Professor National University of Modern Languages, KarachiDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15016161>**Keywords**

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Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

Family as the basic social unit determines the development of individual's personality, coping strategies and communication patterns. The influence of family system theory is well documented in literature. A step ahead will take us to ecological theory which extends this influence to school, peers and community, when individual embraces all these stages of socialization, he obviously faces hurdles and frustrations as the path is not always smooth for all. For few it is very tough either due to some obstruction in the environment in the form of parenting, poor social circles or weak personality which gives rise to poor problem solving. Resorting to substance is one such example. In order to examine the effect of family on substance use, quantitative research design was followed with a sample of 514 individuals, 257 substance users and 257 non-substance users were drawn randomly. The Perceived Mother Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire, (Rohner, 1980) Urdu Version by Malik (2012) was used. In order to conduct the comparative analysis between the two groups t' test for independent sample was administered, further the predictive relationship was assessed through the linear regression, furthermore, the effect size was also calculated. Results supports the theoretical basis of the problem of substance use disorder.

INTRODUCTION

Bronfenbrenner (1979) proposed ecological system theory of development with multilayer sources of influences that affect the child and vice versa. His immediate family, school, peers, extended family, neighborhood, parents' workplace, community, social and political condition around him. According to him conflict in any of the layers may spread throughout the other layers as well. The immediate environment ie; microsystem consists of his family, school and childcare environment. Developmentalists say that a synchrony develops between infant and caretaker from the very first day. The way the care taker responds to infant's need determines the quality of their relationship. The parenting style determines the direction of relationship on the course of development, whether the parent attends his needs with affection or

considers him as a burden and rejects him or neglect him. Martin and Macobby (1983) proposed important element of parenting style that revolves either around demandingness or responsiveness or both. Different parental values, behaviors and practices are reflected through these styles. Baumrind's (1991) parenting styles are different in their emphasis on demandingness and responsiveness. Authoritarian parenting style is reported to be high on demandingness and low on responsiveness. Indulgent parents are high on responsiveness and low on demandingness. Uninvolved parents are low on both demandingness and responsiveness and authoritative parents are high on both demanding and responsive, they are supportive and assertive.

Parental warmth, affection and acceptance play a pivotal role in the development of healthy and proactive personality. Rohner's (2011) parental acceptance rejection theory has implication for the developing child's personality, when the child's need for affection is not met with, he resorts to unhealthy ways to cope with anxiety, which may have internalizing consequences, such as depression or externalizing consequence such as delinquency and substance use and behavioral problems like conduct disorder (Rohner and Britner (2002). Out of these, substance use is that disorder that disrupts the entire family, financially as well as emotionally. However, the exploration of the effect of parental acceptance, warmth and neglect with reference to substance use disorder is an imperative in a resource scarce and stress ridden society like Pakistan, where both micro and macro level variables impact the individual.

As the current study focuses on the microsystem of socialization and its consequences. Parent- child relationship is viewed as a kind of interaction which starts immediately after birth. This interaction is initiated infant when he makes sound like crying and care giver responds him, this process is known as "synchrony". when the response of adult meets the need of infant, the synchrony develops well with positive implication, if results in thwarting of needs, it results in poor attachment (Moore,2007). The topic will start with the analysis of theory and related literature.

Parental acceptance rejection theory, as postulated by Rohner (2008) can be conceived as a continuum, at one end there is acceptance, which give the feelings of warmth and affection. At the other end there is rejection which gives the feelings of neglect, aggression, and hostility. However, their negativity does not end around parental relationship rather their whole perception of the world is influenced by this negativity. They hold the cognition of the world as hostile, aggressive and deceptive. They process the information in a way that confirms their cognition (Khaliq and Rohner, 2012). He further explained the coping strategies of rejected individuals who either engage in affective coping without being negatively influenced by their parental rejection or instrumental coping who are task oriented and work well in their professional life despite rejection caused by their parents. Rohner (2016) introduced

sociocultural system model which shows that how different levels of ecological system (family, peers, community, and sociocultural context) are affected by parental rejection. From 1975 to 1986 he studied this concept cross culturally and found that culture which nurture the child, he perceives the supernatural as loving and supportive, culture which rejects the child, he perceives the supernatural as hostile and aggressive.

1. Warmth/ affection is described as any kind of physical and verbal behavior symbolic of love (Rohner,2004).
2. Hostility / aggression is described as internal reaction to anger, when parents' own needs are in clash with that of child they react in verbally aggressive way as being sarcastic or physically aggressive as being punishing physically (Rohner, 2016).
3. Indifferent/ Neglect described as not attending to the physical and psychological needs of the child (Rohner, 2016).
4. Undifferentiated rejection is described as uncaring attitude of parent toward child. Behavioral indicators are not clear as to the parent is aggressive, neglectful or affectionate (Rohner, 2004).

Mathibela and Skhosana (2020) discussed the use of substance among adolescents within the perspective of ecological theory perspective, while highlighting the significance of parent child relationship they emphasized the importance of communication between them, which determines the quality of their relationship and reflects the family functioning as well. Waini (2015) took it a step ahead and said that adolescent's substance use problem lead to marital conflict about how to treat such a child, thus creating a clear causative relationship between adolescent's substance use and distressed parenting and family functioning. According to Methibela and Skhosana (2015) parental discord about adolescent's substance use also disrupts father child relationship, leading to complex emotion, breakdown of family values and resulting in dysfunctional families (Winters et al, 2015).

According to Zastrow and Ashman (2016) ecological system theory assumes that individuals are not separate entities rather interconnected within the system, influencing the environment and vice

versa, where his needs and of the people around him, his peers, school and community impact his behavior. Methileba and Skhosona (2020) concluded that all adolescents face challenges in their lives, parents should provide support and warmth to them to buffer the effects of any challenge. Parents should have open communication channels with their children. A dysfunctional family leaves the adolescent at the mercy of peer influence in the absence of their parental support. Dacey and Kenny (1994) reported that adolescents dissatisfied with their family are more likely to take drugs than those who were satisfied with their family. Moreover, emotional intimacy with parent were less likely to indulge in drug abuse (Coombs et al, (1991).

At micro level of ecological system theory, parental role has been analyzed in the lives of drug addicts by Riaz and Soomro (2021), they found that substance users perceived their parents as more neglectful, aggressive and less controlling. This has been supported by Munaf (2004), according to her parental rejection has also been identified as strong determinants of acting out and externalizing behaviour problems including substance abuse, her results showed higher scores of misconducts among those who perceive their parents as rejecting. Baumrind's (1991) parenting style particularly authoritative which is the blend of behavioral control and open communication channel has been best described as best protective factor against substance use and externalizing problems. Furthermore, Maccoby and Martin (1983) identified parental control and demandingness dimensions in their parenting theory. Behavioral control has been recommended as a protective factor and psychological control as leading to guilt and shame (Barber, 1996).

Son et al (2020) studied maternal rejection within the framework of family, community and sociocultural perspective, their cross cultural study found strong impact of maternal rejection on the development of child.

Rothenberg (2022) studied parental acceptance and rejection in relation to children's externalizing and internalizing behaviors cross culturally. They found that cultures that were high on indifference were also high on internalizing problem as compared to those cultures who were low on indifference. Moreover,

Glavak and Sakoman (2003) confirmed the theory's conjecture that child rearing practices particularly mother's role on child's subsequent development, their results showed that addicts perceive themselves as significantly rejected by their mothers as compared to non addicts.

Glavak and Sakoman (2003) showed that substance users in his sample reported less satisfaction with their families and relationship with their mothers, but their fathers were more reported as rejecting, neglectful and less warm. They identified mothers' rejection as major risk factor for substance use.

Sajid and Riaz (2016) studied perceived parental rejection and its impact on psychological adjustment on a group of convicts and found that parental rejection specifically neglect and indifference as strong predictor of psychological problems. Brewer (2017) found that parental involvement is a strong protective factor against drug abuse. Hafeez (2020) found that mother acceptance is a strong predictor of emotional intelligence as compared to those who showed maternal rejection.

Teichman and Kafir (2000) identified several risk factors of substance use which include family, peers, media and community, among these family has been reported as the strongest risk factor.

The present study of all these microlevel variables on the individual particularly in relation to substance use. It was hypothesized that there would be a significant difference between adult substance users and on the variables of (a). Perceived Mother's Warmth /Affection, (b) Perceived Mother's Hostility / Aggression, (c) Perceived) Perceived Mother's Undifferentiated Rejection, and Perceived Mother's Acceptance and Rejection Scores. It was further assumed that there would be a predictive relationship between parental acceptance and rejection scores and the subscales of hostility, aggression, and undifferentiated rejection.

METHOD

Participants

To select the sample random sampling method was used. Participants were 514 adults whose age range from 18 to 40. Mean age of substance use group was 27 and for non-substance user it was 34. They primarily came from (middle and lower) socioeconomic backgrounds and lived in both

nuclear and joint families. The group of substance users consisted of 257 adults, and the other group consisted of 257 without any substance use. The sample size was drawn with the help of G* power with effect size 3, probability of error .05 and power .95 (Faul et al, 2009). All those who have been identified as having a substance use disorder on the basis of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-V), diagnosed by clinical psychologists, sociologists, and rehabilitative experts. (American Psychiatric Association, 2014). They were contacted by various treatment facilities in Karachi, Pakistan. However, the second group of participants, was chosen from the general community. They were all chosen using convenient sampling technique. All three socioeconomic classes, including upper, middle, and lower socioeconomic backgrounds, were represented among the participants in the non-substance users group. To study this issue quantitative research design with comparative approach was adopted.

Measures

Demographic Information Form

Demographic data was gathered with the main focus of the question was on the participant's gender, age, education, marital status, number of siblings, birth order, family structure, socioeconomic status, type of addiction, cause of addiction, length of use of addictive substances, and presence of any family members who also use addictive substances.

Perceived Mother Acceptance - Rejection Questionnaire, Adult (Rohner 1981)

The Perceived Mother Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire, Adult (PARQ, translated into Urdu) asks respondents to rate their childhood experiences in terms of paternal warmth (i.e. acceptance-rejection). In this scale, respondents rated parental behavior as (a) perceived warmth and affection, (b) perceived hostility and aggression, (c) perceived indifference and neglect, and (d) perceived undifferentiated rejection. are evaluated on four scales. The Likert scale range is almost always true (4). Sometimes true (3), rarely true (2), and rarely true (1).

Total scores indicate perceived acceptance of maternal rejection.

The PARQ Urdu version translated by Malik (2012) was used to facilitate participants' understanding. The validity and reliability of test results can be displayed as a string using a calculated alpha factor between 0.80 and 0.95. The Cronbach alpha value was found to be 0.92, so the internal consistency of the scale is very high. A recent study found this scale to be reliable as well, confirming Cronbach's alpha tolerance for mothers ($\alpha=.91$) and fathers ($\alpha=.87$) for internal consistency.

Ethical considerations

Permission was sought from Advanced studies and research board to carry out the research. The authorities of rehabilitation centers were given detail description of study. The purpose of research was shared with the participants and informed consent was sought through consent form. All of the participants received assurances that their information would be kept confidential, will be used only for study, and that their cooperation would be greatly valued. Additionally, individuals were told that they have right to withdraw at any moment if they are not willing to disclose their personal information. Permission was also sought from the author of the scale.

Procedure

After getting permission from research review board persons with substance use disorder were approached through various drug treatment and rehabilitation centers by taking formal written permission. Once the rapport was established, they were provided a consent form to seek their permission. Later demographic sheet containing personal information was filled out with each respondent, and PARQ questionnaire was administered, their queries were also handled effectively. Furthermore, respondents with substance used disorder were asked as to how their real mothers treat them during their childhood. The total procedure took almost 30 minutes. The second group of participants were approached from normal population and they mainly belonged to institutes and community.

RESULTS

Table 1

descriptive statistics of Group 1 Group 2 on Religion, Marital Status, family structure, and socioeconomic level of Participants (N=514)

Variables	Group 1		Group 2	
	N	%	N	%
Religion				
Muslims	254	98	254	98
Hinduism	2	0.007	2	0.07
Christianity	1	0.003	3	0.011
Marital status				
Married	118	45	57	22
Unmarried	135	52	197	76
Divorced	4	0.15	3	1
Family system				
Joint family system	145	56	193	75
Nuclear family system	112	43	64	25
SES				
Lower	91	23	10	3.3
Middle	137	53	208	69.3
Upper Middle	29	11	82	27.3
Upper Extreme	0	0	0	0

Table 1 indicates the scores of participants on the demographic variables of religion, marital status, family system and socioeconomic status

Table 2: Reliability Analysis (Cronbach alpha value) of Perceived Acceptance Rejection Scale Adult

Measures of Research	Number of Items	α
Perceived Acceptance Rejection Scale	60	.68

Table 2 indicates that Perceived Acceptance Rejection Scale has reliability coefficient of .68 with the current sample

Table 3

mean differences of substance user and non user on total PARQ scores

Groups	N	M	SD	T	P	effect size
Substance user	257	.0501	1.057	1.207	.228	.0990
Non substance user	257	.0488	.940			

Table 3 indicates that there is no significant difference between substance users and non- users on Parental Acceptance and rejection scores. $P > .5$, effect size small,

Table 4

Mean differences in all the subscales between substance user and non substance user

Variable	group	N	M	SD	t	p
Warmth	substance user	257	58.86	13.397	-9.81	.000
	Non user	257	68.01	10.84		
Neglect	substance user	257	36.83	3.416	1.752	.080
	Non user	257	36.33	3.525		
Aggression	substance user	257	33.56	12.35	7.99	.000
	Non user	257	29.90	7.412		
Undifferentiated Rejection	substance user	257	22.66	8.240	6.124	.000
	non user	257	19.25	5.103		

Table 4 indicates that both the groups differ on the variables of warmth, aggression, and undifferentiated rejection, $p < .05$ but do not differ on the variable of neglect $p > .05$

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Table 5

Summary of Linear Regression Analysis with all subscales as predictor of PARQ scores in substance users (N=257)

Predictors	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	df	Sig.
Neglect		.391		189.73	255	.000*
Rejection	.626a	.481	.399	273.751		.000
Aggression	.725	.526	.524	326.940		.000
Warmth	.189	.036	.033	10.497		.001

Table 5 indicates that all variables predict parental rejection $p < .05$ and the model is 39, 48,52 & 3% is explained user and non-user on the variable of parental acceptance and rejection. The results showed that substance user mean scores of both the groups were insignificant. Glavak and Sakoman (2003) also showed no significant difference between the scores of substance user and non user. The overall sample seems to have issue with parental acceptance, this

DISCUSSION

The present study was conducted to find the impact of maternal acceptance and rejection on substance and non-substance user. On the basis of existing literature, it was hypothesized that there would be a significant difference in the mean scores of substance

sheds light on the fact that parenting requires special attention in society. There is a possibility that non substance use group might have some other kind of problem as a result of such parenting other than substance use. Another possibility is to explore their coping methods as well because if despite being identified as normal people, they have problem with their parents then they must be engaged in coping that is either proactive or emotional. The mesosystem also play protective role where parental rejection is mitigated by some close peer and significant other. Indulging in substance use is one among many reactions that take place because of parental rejection. The magnitude of difference is very small. The underlying theory of parental acceptance and rejection makes the same assertion, stating that individuals who perceive their mothers as rejecting fall prey to substance use, the same has been reported by Sajid and Riaz (2016). Their respondents being convicts reported more parental rejection than the normal group. The analysis of the subscales of parental acceptance and rejection scale revealed significant difference on the variable of warmth, aggression, and rejection, only on neglect the difference is insignificant. Rohner (1986) writes that child depends on adult for his emotional needs, acceptance, approval, love and appreciation, if these are not met with, the child may develop maladaptive behaviors, of which substance use is one, which they resort to as a coping. Moreover, Forsman (2008) reported that parental acceptance and unconditional positive regard leads to higher self-esteem as compared to those who perceived their mothers as rejecting and reported lower self-esteem, so acceptance is essential to life satisfaction and wellbeing of an individual.

The results also showed high mean differences in the mean scores on warmth and affection between substance users and non substance users. Etkins et al (2014) reported low warmth as a cause of externalizing behavior. Glavak and Sakoman's (2003) results showed significant difference in the scores of substance user and non user on the variable of warmth. Moreover, Xing et al (2018) research also supports existing result that parental aggression leads to externalizing behavior among whereas non addicts' mean scores on warmth marks secure relationship with parents as a precursor of healthy

personality. Chaplin et al (2012) and Moore et al (2004) in their study mention the same point that close parent child relationship can buffer the effects of two extremes authoritarian and permissive parenting.

Riaz and Soomro (2021) reported that substance users perceive their father and mother as rejecting, aggressive and neglectful as compared to non-user counterpart. Bares et al (2011) support the result that authoritative parenting style is a protective factor against substance use among young people whereas, neglectful style has been reported as a great risk factor where lack of monitoring and supervision leave them at the risk of falling prey to the negative influences of mesosystem where school, peers, religious gatherings, and extended family. Moreover, Brewer's (2017) study also support the result of current study that parental involvement, warmth, consistent discipline prevents children from becoming substance users.

All the subscales including warmth, neglect, aggression, and rejection predict the parental acceptance rejection scores, where these variables prove that 3%, 39 %,52%, and48% of the model is explained respectively. Campo and Rohner (1992) state that parental acceptance and rejection has predictive and consistent effect on children. Sajid and Riaz (2016) reported indifference and neglect as a predictor of criminal behaviors. These researches support the result of current study where strong and significant predictive relationship between parental acceptance, rejection and subscales of neglect, hostility, and undifferentiated rejection have been found. Overall results support the hypotheses that both the groups differ on all the variables of parental acceptance and rejection and parental warmth, hostility and undifferentiated rejection predict the relation with parental acceptance and rejection.

Conclusion

Child rearing practices are corner stone of development on which the whole edifice of personality is built. Parental behavior has profound effect on child's personality. The way the parent treat their child either with warmth or anger, hostility or indifference all lead them to different direction. Those who receive acceptance and warmth have trustworthy relationship with their parents and in

times of stress they share their burden with their parents. Those who face rejection have poor communication with their parents and in times of stress there are more chances that they indulge in externalizing behavior like criminal activities and substance use.

Limitations and suggestions

A nationwide sample size would make it more generalizable.

If different ethnic groups were also identified, then those communities could be approached for prevention and rehabilitation program

As substance use disorder is hardly reported does not mean that such a problem does not exist among them. Consequently, their accessibility could change the picture of results.

Educational and socioeconomic variables could have been calculated and their impact be explored.

As Pakistan is not a stable country economically and politically. This has been a part of war zone, where inflow of different drugs has been common since years. People face extreme economic pressures and to avoid people seek refuge in drugs.

Implications

Parents represent the basic unit of socialization, according to Maccoby & Martin (1983) parents should provide structured environment and contingency plan to teach the children self regulation. This will lead them to inhibit destructive behavior.

There must be educational plans regarding marriage and parenthood like why one wants to become a parent. What picture one has of one’s future family? and what strategies he/she has to achieve that goal?

Media can play a very effective role in shaping the direction of parenting. Parental counseling be arranged in schools and community. Educational institutions can play a vigil role in this regard by adding counselor in their staff. Medical examination be conducted in educational institutions, if there is doubt about the use of substance.

Parents as the primary agents of socialization play a crucial role in the development of child’s personality. Mother being a person who spends greatest of her time with her child affects him most that’s why her affection and warmth can take the child to the height of satisfaction whereas, her neglectful behavior

makes him vulnerable to minor influences that can affect him negatively. Parental warmth has implication for becoming a healthy citizen who respects social and parental values and neglect can lead him to become disruptive individual of society (Brooks, 2004).

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